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“LITERARY ANALYSIS OF THE FILM PERCY JACKSON”

The Lightning Thief is at heart a fantasy-adventure film based on Greek mythology for a contemporary setting written by Rick Riordan and directed by Chris Columbus. The story centers on the 12-year-old Percy Jackson who is Poseidon’s demigod son and is accused of stealing the lightning bolt of Zeus, the supreme god of the Olympians. Zeus gives Poseidon fourteen days to return the bolt stolen by his son and threatens him that if the master bolt will not be returned to Mount Olympus before summer solstice, he will initiate war among all the gods.

Meanwhile, in the real world, Percy, unaware of his true identity as the son of Poseidon, the god of the sea, appears to his peers to be dyslexic and has a unique ability to stay underwater for a long time. He has trouble behaving in school. One reason why he does not or cannot blend well with others that easy aside from being a *half-human* demigod is his unfortunate fate and that is, he has never met his father ever since. His abusive stepfather raises him, so the only person whom he draws energy from is his loving mother. It feels like his life is cursed by a total darkness.

Percy’s fast-paced and heroic journey starts on a school trip to a local museum where his friends, Annabeth Chase and Grover Underwood, accompany him. Percy was shocked when his Math teacher, Mrs. Dodds, transforms into one of the three Furies of Greek myth and attacks him, which it later turns into dust and disappears. When he returns to his friends to report what has happened, they tell Percy that they don’t have a teacher named Dodds that he is just hallucinating.

Just after Percy’s sixth-grade, Sally, his mother, and Percy go on a summer trip to the beach. Grover, whom Percy thought a human teenager but a young satyr, surprises the two with his visit. Grover visits them to warn the two that they are in danger and brings them to a mysterious summer camp. However, upon their arrival, a Minotaur attacks them and abducts Sally as she dissolves into a blinding flash of gold light before Percy can help her. Perplexed by these horrible events Percy is experiencing, he is convinced that there is something different about him and discovers that his mother is in the underworld with Hades until he learns straight from Grover that he is a half-blood, half-human, and half-god, so Grover takes him into a camp life where he meets several other demigods and where he begins to learn more about himself and his godly parent and reveal his powers as a demigod.

To retrieve Zeus’s master bolt, which is believed to be in the realm of Hades in the underworld, Percy sets out on a quest together with Annabeth, the smart daughter of Athena, and Grover. On their journey, the three defeat several mythological monsters like Medusa and Chimera and finally find Hades who also accuses

Percy of stealing his Helm of Darkness (his symbol of power) and threatens him to kill his mother if he will not return it to him. Clueless of the indictments of Zeus and Hades, Percy proves to them that he is not the thief but the god Ares who has all the missing items and has been manipulating everybody that he is a friend. Hence Percy confronts Ares and challenges him into fight. Stabbed in the heel, Ares surrenders the Helm of Darkness to Percy which he gives it to Hades. Hades then realizes that Percy is innocent. Also, Percy takes the lightning bolt back to its rightful owner, Zeus. Zeus then accepts the bolt and allows Percy to have a short talk with his father, Poseidon, before he return to Camp Half-Blood where he learns that his mother is alive and waits for him.

When he returns to the camp, Percy receives the camp beads as an award for his deeds and is given the choice of whether to return home and leave the camp with his mother or to just stay there with the other demigods. After much thought Percy decides to leave the camp for his mother and to attend another school his mother has found. Percy just knows what is right.

Affected Issues Related to the Work

I believe most, if not all, can relate to Percy in some diverse and individualized ways. We go through life uncomfortable with uncertainty. We are haunted by the so many *What if* questions in life that no one can provide an answer. Some are afraid to go beyond their comfort zone without knowing that crossing it reveals an opportunity to explore more about themselves that could strengthen their own beliefs, viewpoints, abilities, and other ethical properties. It is also worth noting that there are people along the way who come to help you achieve your goal and reach your destination with less struggles. I call them friends and mentors. Like how Percy perceives it when he is at the camp, we have to understand that trust is a fragile thing and it should only be given to people who truly deserve it. Things become so unfortunate when we start investing our trust to people and suddenly would break it as they enjoy sitting in the front row while feasting on our downfall. However, it is still good to remind ourselves to always be kind to unkind people, for they it the most.

Another issue that I have to raise is on Percy's immeasurable love for his mother. After Percy knew that his mother was Hade's captive, he did not hesitate of saving her and even moved heaven and earth just to get there. He was focused and determined to hone his abilities so to save his mother from Hades. I wonder if how many of us today can equate that when our loved ones are in great danger or in need of our help. Sadly, some teens today don't know how to respect their parents. They come to believe that when their right age comes, they can journey the world on their own or worse, abuse alcohol or drugs often.

This may sound off tangent but it seems that teenagers today don't have lots of staying power lately. Impulsively, they tackle new interest, then, get bored or overwhelmed, and quit too easily. Yes, they have no attention span. Things just keep changing. Just for a fleeting split second they keep changing phone number, friends, significant other, get-up, mood, food, plans, gadgets, job preferences, and even their dreams. Oh, I'm reminded. The truth of the matter is they often allow their fertile imagination from media free rein to blow things out of proportion, strong enough to enslave me. This basically explains why they don't stay the course at some point and don't get sidetracked by people giving out unsolicited advice even if it is coming from their parents. They try to grow up so fast and busy themselves looking for a partner and rush into a relationship at a very young age. I don't exactly understand how their morals are flawed letting technology take over their life.

Another indispensable lesson I got from watching Percy Jackson's Lightning Thief film can be summed up in this line, "Pride is concerned with who is right; humility is concerned with what is right." In the film, Percy got

bullied by a lot of students and would beat Percy up every chance they got. Despite the criticism he received, he never showed any emotion even if he knew at that time that he could defend himself from the bullies. He just did not want to hurt any of them. He took a step back, and for me that makes him a hero. You don't have to indulge in a physical fight just so you know you are stronger than others. He has a very kind and pure heart. Good for Percy because he can control his emotion before it blurts out. How about you?

I can't imagine myself If I were Percy. I have been bullied too by a lot of people from elementary to college. Nobody compelled me to rise. The bullies taught me how to fold my hands and acquiesce despite the scowling, growling, and fussing. Every step I trotted was spattered with tears and blatant learnings I collected in my haste to ascend this far. To underscore, bullying has been very alarming. Like Percy and I, I know there are several students who have experienced bullying, may it be a verbal harassment, physical assault or coercion, or grounds on religion, race, gender, and ability. Instead of shouting or fighting back, like how Percy did, walk away and stay away from them if speaking up in a calm, clear voice seems too hard or not safe to do. If they still bully you, I think it is high time to open up to your parents who will report it to the people concerned.

Literary Techniques

Symbolism

The lightning bolt is very symbolic. It symbolizes loss of ignorance. The missing of it calls for a major war that no one has ever seen before. It also represents the punishment of humans from the gods once it goes missing. In other words lightning bolt signals a terrible conflict among the gods and humans, for it is a weapon of mass destruction and an ultimate symbol of Zeus' power.

Also, water symbolizes Percy's special weapon. In fact, he considers it his life source. He is able to manipulate it even at first he does not fully understand his skill. It has started when Percy notices that he can stay for a few minutes at the bottom of the swimming pool. Not only that, it is proven after the fight between Percy and Annabeth that water can heal his wounds. Percy is able to defeat any kind of monsters in the way through his incredible control of water.

Setting

There are major and minor settings seen in the story. The story is set in modern day in New York City. When Percy has found out that he is a demigod, he is sent to summer camp at Camp Half-blood. From the camp, Percy and his friends have journeyed across America to Los Angeles where they are able to find the site of the gates to the underworld in the quest of finding the missing lightning bolt.

Theme

The story circles around the theme of identity. Percy Jackson at the beginning of the story does not know anything about his real father or even his real identity after noticing that there is something wrong with him when is with his ordinary friends and classmates. No one in the ordinary world realizes that Percy is in fact a hero. He describes himself a "bad kid" since he always gets into trouble until he becomes more himself when he is sent to the camp where he feels he really belongs. With the help of Grover, Percy understands deeper who he is and what he can do. Grover introduces him to the other teens similar to himself (demigods) who later help him discover his hidden abilities of sword-fighting and battle skills.

Conflict

Percy seems to have many major internal conflicts in the story. First he feels like nobody understands him and finds it hard to connect with other kids around. He has great anger towards his father, Poseidon, for letting him live in ignorance not giving him the chance to know who he really is. This is really hard for him since the only person whom he can run to and draw energy from is his mother, Sally. It even gets worse when monsters coming from nowhere constantly following him and attacking him. That is where he sense that there is a danger waiting ahead of him and that he has to push his physical limits to fight against them.

Tone

According to Kristine Tucker (2015), Riordan, the author of *Lightning Thief*, uses sarcastic but friendly tone referring to Percy's wit and casual adolescent-inspired conversations. She also pointed out that the lively and suspenseful tone helps establish a mood of expectation to captivate readers as Percy vaporizes his pre-Algebra teacher with a magic sword, fights a Minotaur, and resolves conflicts between Zeus and Poseidon.

Figurative Language

Personification: "It was like looking at the ocean: some days, you could tell what mood it was in. Most days, though, unreadable, mysterious." In this case, the ocean is given emotions as if it were like humans.

Simile: "I was holding back the tide by force of will, but tension was building like carbonation behind a cork."

Allusion: Annabeth's fear of spiders, the Minotaur, the Lotus Hotel and Casino, the appearance of Echidna and Chimera, and Charon's acceptance of the monetary bribe to get to the trio to the Underworld.

Character Archetypes

Percy Jackson is the Initiate archetype since he is the protagonist of the story. He undergoes training at the camp on how to use his powers and control them.

Grover is the Supernatural helper who aids Percy in his quest of finding the missing bolt in return of saving his mother from Hades, the god of darkness.

Annabeth has an archetype of an Earth mother since she is full of knowledge and fertility. Among them, Grover and Percy, she is the wisest like her mother, Athena, the goddess of wisdom and strategy. She is the one who also helps Grover and Percy succeed in getting back Sally as they journey across America.

Supernatural Intervention

There is divine intervention happened when Poseidon speaks to Percy, Athena speaks to Annabeth, and water heals Percy.

Response from Viewers

“*The Lightning Thief* works mostly because it’s a good idea. It’s *Harry Potter* meets the *X-Men*, set to the tune of all the crazy Greek mythology you learned in grammar school. That’s too much fun to be ruined, the books on which it’s based are full of too many good ideas to be torpedoed by lazy filmmaking. Now that I’ve seen it, I’m off to read the books. Don’t bother with the sequel, I’ll catch it in print.” – **Josh Tyler**, blogger (Cinemablend.com)

“The plot uses the presence of the Greek gods as an indistinct outline to influence teenagers who are more interested in the prestige and glamor of their connection than the responsibility that comes with it.” – **David Kayes** (Cinemaphile.org)

“Not a perfect film, but the movie does have a certain passion that a lot of other franchise attempts have lacked. If you like Greek mythology and are looking for an antidote to *Clash of the Titans*, this may be what you are looking for.” – Wesley Lovell (Cinema Sight)

Percy Jackson compared to Joseph Campbell’s Monomyth

Call to Adventure: Percy’s call to adventure starts when he joins the fieldtrip to the museum to look at statues of some Greek mythology figures. There are writings (something Greek stuff) embossed below every statue that nobody could understand and read but him. His teacher suddenly transforms to a monster and attacks him during the school fieldtrip. After that incident, his mother gets stolen by Hades and the only way to get his mother back is by returning the missing lightning bolt to its rightful owner, Zeus, because Zeus accuses him of stealing it.

Supernatural Aid/Amulet: Percy’s natural aid and protector is his satyr friend, Grover who helps him throughout his whole journey. Along with Grover, Annabeth also accompanies Percy on his quest to save his mother since she has a lot of experience in battle and is the brains in their journey. Meanwhile, Mr. Brunner, Percy’s Camp mentor, gives him a pen that turns into a magical sword.

Crossing the Threshold: Percy Jackson leaving the ordinary world enters the camp half-blood and finds out that he is not just an ordinary boy but a demigod who possesses hidden powers. There he meets other teens who also are demigods. It feels like it is the place where he should be.

Road of Trials: The three, Percy, Grover, and Annabeth, go through three main trials. The first one is their encounter with Medusa. Their mission is to get the pearl without looking at Medusa’s eyes; otherwise, they all turn into statues. After Medusa, they face and fight the hydra, a monster from Greek myths. Lastly, they go to the Lotus Hotel and Casino in Las Vegas where they eat the lotus flowers which dull their senses making them never want to leave the place.

Meeting with the Goddess: To get Percy’s mother back, the three find a way to get to the Underworld. There they meet Persephone, queen of the Underworld and wife of Hades, who helps them escape by stealing the lightning bolt from Hades, the main culprit, so they could return it to Zeus.

Flight: Percy is able to fly back to the Empire building to return the lightning bolt that Zeus once accuses him of stealing it.

Atonement with the Father: Since Percy proves to Zeus that his indictment is wrong, Zeus then grants him the chance to talk to his father, Poseidon, who asks Percy for forgiveness for abandoning him and his mother.

The Ultimate Boon: It is when he escapes the Underworld with his mother and returns the bolt back to Olympus. I also think that being able to discover his real identity that he is a hero and a demigod and meet his father is already his greatest ultimate boon.

Return Home: Percy together with Grover, Annabeth and his mother return to the camp where he is given beads as an award of his bravery and loyalty. Now he has to decide whether to stay in the camp and spend more of his years with the other demigods or to go with his mother in the ordinary world. Guess what? He chooses the latter. He chooses the freedom to live.

